

DQRL-Based Dynamic Resource Allocation for Energy-Spectral Efficient Next-Generation Clustered Radio Access Networks

Mohammad Eskandarinia
ISI/ATHENA, Patras, Greece
and Universitat Politècnica
de Catalunya
(UPC), Barcelona, Spain
meskandarinia@isi.gr

John S. Vardakas
Dept. of Informatics
UOWM, Kastoria, Greece, and
Iquadrat Informatica,
Barcelona, Spain
jvardakas@iquadrat.com

Golshan Famitafreshi
Iquadrat Informatica,
Barcelona, Spain
g.famitafreshi@iquadrat.com

Christos Verikoukis
CEID, University of Patras,
Greece, and
ISI/ATHENA, Patras, Greece
cveri@upatras.gr

Abstract—In next-generation Radio Access Networks (RAN), dynamically and intelligently selecting Radio Units (RUs) with varying power levels is essential to maximize throughput, ensure energy efficiency, and maintain reliable transmission quality. The 6G paradigm relies heavily on real-time adaptive decision-making, requiring an optimal RUs assignment for each User Equipment (UE) based on critical parameters such as Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), transmit power, Spectral Efficiency (SE) and traffic load. To achieve this, we propose a Deep Q-Reinforcement Learning (DQRL)-based framework that evaluates the SNR between all possible UE-RU pairs under different power configurations. The framework optimizes its selection policy by balancing energy efficiency and transmission quality, encoded in a carefully designed reward function. Initially, the agent explores the environment through random RU selection (exploration phase), but over time, it transitions to an epsilon-greedy policy, gradually favoring high-reward actions to minimize power consumption while sustaining Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. By continuously refining its policy through interactions with the network environment, the DQRL agent converges to an optimal strategy that dynamically allocates UEs in each time interval, achieves a strong trade off between Energy Efficiency (EE) and SE compared to static or heuristic approaches. This method ensures scalable and intelligent resource management in 6G networks, adapting to fluctuating channel conditions and traffic demands.

Index Terms—O-RAN, near-RT RIC, cell-free massive MIMO, mmWave, energy efficiency, spectral efficiency, deep reinforcement learning, Deep Q-Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapidly increasing demand for reliable and high speed internet connectivity is driving RAN toward more advanced and intelligent architectural designs. Recent developments show that intelligent, environment aware techniques such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) based RAN slicing [1] and flexible resource sharing in Cell-Free (CF) massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (mMIMO) systems [2] can simultaneously enhance QoS and reduce power consumption compared to networks that rely on static, non adaptive configurations [3].

In this paper, we present a model that helps reduce power consumption in millimeter Wave (mmWave) RUs deployed within CF architectures. The proposed model facilitates more

efficient network planning by providing an initial estimate of RU power usage, while also supporting future adaptation through dynamic adjustments based on traffic load.

The main idea of our work is to employ intelligent, time-aware selection methods to achieve the best network performance. Prior studies such as [4] and [5], have used metrics like effective channel gain to guide RU selection, while the work in [6] focused mainly on energy consumption without incorporating adaptive or learning driven methods. Other research efforts that have explored Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) for power optimization [7] were built upon network architectures that do not align with modern CF mMIMO requirements or the spectral efficiency targets anticipated for 6G systems.

In contrast, this work introduces an O-RAN based CF mMIMO control framework in which each RU can operate in either active or sleep mode under a realistic, state dependent power model. This design enables the learning agent to exploit energy saving opportunities while accounting for RU activation costs. A hybrid channel model is incorporated to capture spatial fading dynamics, thereby supporting more robust RL driven decisions across heterogeneous propagation environments. RU activation and power level selection are formulated as a multi objective reinforcement learning problem, where the agent dynamically balances spectral and energy efficiency and naturally learns to switch RUs to sleep when $\alpha = 1$ (pure EE mode). Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed approach achieves energy reductions while maintaining competitive spectral efficiency across different UE densities. Our work highlights the important role of intelligent network control in future wireless systems, where adapting system parameters based on traffic, network structure, and time conditions can significantly improve overall performance. To enable a clear comparison with prior work, we consider five key aspects: (i) intelligent network control, (ii) explicit modeling of RU power consumption cost, (iii) spectral efficiency awareness, (iv) a CF mMIMO architecture, and (v) operation in mmWave, terahertz bands. Existing studies typically address only a subset of these

Fig. 1: O-RAN control via a near RT RIC hosting the DQRL agent. Left ($\alpha = 1$): energy centric operation activates the minimum RU subset per user centric cluster and favors low transmit power. Right ($\alpha = 0$): SE centric operation favors high gain RU selection and higher transmit power to maximize throughput.

aspects. For example, [1] focuses on selected dimensions but does not explicitly incorporate RU power cost modeling in the O-RAN control loop; [2] studies CF systems without learning driven control and without mmWave, THz considerations; [3] considers dynamic allocation in a conventional (cell-based) setting and does not jointly address learning based control, CF architecture, and SE aware design. In contrast, this work jointly addresses all five aspects by designing a deployable DQRL policy that selects RU activation and transmit power levels. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model, power consumption assumptions and introduces the proposed DQRL based agent and reward design. Section III discusses implementation details and simulation results and at last Section IV concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we consider a mMIMO system in which the number of antennas is significantly larger than the number of users. This configuration enables the use of Zero Forcing precoding (ZF) in the Downlink (DL) phase to cancel out interference between users connected to the same RU. Although some cross tier interference may persist, Space Division Multiplexing (SDM) allows multiple users to be served on the same time frequency resources with sufficiently high spatial separation. As a result, residual interference becomes negligible, resulting in a more linear and interpretable relationship between the received SNR and achievable performance. In this setup, the system can deactivate a subset of RUs in each time slot to improve energy efficiency without degrading service quality. However, this introduces a dynamic optimization challenge, as the system must balance EE and SE and adjust its policy under varying traffic and channel conditions. This approach helps save energy while still ensuring reliable performance. In each episode, a

different number of user UEs enter. We also assume high user mobility within each episode. To calculate the time interval where channel hardening occurs, we use the formula (1) as shown below [8].

$$T_c = \lambda / (4v) \quad (1)$$

where T_c is coherence time (time interval) and λ is wavelength and v is the velocity of UEs.

A. Policy And Channel Model

We consider a CF mMIMO system with M randomly distributed antennas and K randomly distributed users, where $M \gg K$ [2]. As illustrated in Fig.1, all RUs are connected to Open RAN (O-RAN) Distributed Units (O-DUs), which in turn connect to a central controller, the O-RAN Central Unit (O-CU), via the fronthaul network. A near Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (near RT RIC) hosts the proposed agent, which manages the entire system as a single cell without boundaries. This architecture enables payload data and power control information to be exchanged seamlessly between UEs and RUs.

In this setup, all RUs can simultaneously serve all users through spatial multiplexing, leveraging the large antenna array relative to the number of users. The agent adapts the system policy according to the trade-off coefficient α . When $\alpha \approx 0$, the system prioritizes SE, leading UEs to associate with RUs that provide maximum channel gain and use higher transmission power. Conversely, When $\alpha \approx 1$, the system emphasizes EE, by deactivating unnecessary RUs and lowering transmission power, thereby reducing overall energy consumption. The wireless channel is modeled using a combination of Rician and Rayleigh fading. For line of sight (LoS) links shorter than 200 meters, the Rician model is applied; for non LoS (NLoS) links, Rayleigh fading is assumed [9]. The model incorporates both the deterministic LoS component and the

scattered NLoS component. Furthermore, we employ a 2D channel representation [10] that accounts for both azimuth and elevation angles, ensuring a more realistic characterization of the wireless environment.

B. Power Consumption Model

In a CF architecture, baseband processing and power amplification are handled by the central unit. As a result, most of the power used by each RU comes from its Radio Frequency (RF) components, such as mixers, Analog to Digital and Digital to Analog converters (ADCs/DACs), and beamforming circuits [11] [12]. In our model, we assume each RU consumes a fixed power in active mode and small constant at sleep phase. This value is based on scaled-down LTE RF systems, which typically consume 20 to 50 watts in active mode for macro-cells, and adjusted to account for the higher efficiency of mmWave systems (which use less power per antenna).

C. Deep Q-Reinforcement Learning Model

As depicted in Fig.1, agent located inside the near RT RIC, operates based on a defined policy, which aims to minimize EE or increasing SE depending on condition while maintaining communication quality. The agent selects both the transmission power level and the RU selection in each time interval. In every defined time slot, new traffic enters the simulated environment. With this new traffic, it forms a multi-dimensional SNR and SE matrices [13] for different transmission power levels. These matrices helps the agent evaluate which RU and power level combination is optimal at that moment according to policy. Equation (2) and Equation (3) shows how the SNR and SE are calculated in our model.

$$SNR_{km} = \frac{p_{km} |\mathbf{h}_{km}^H \mathbf{w}_{km}|^2}{\sigma^2}. \quad (2)$$

$$SE_{km} = \log_2(1 + SNR_{km}) \quad [\text{bps/Hz}] \quad (3)$$

Where P_{km} is transmission power of m-th antenna during the DL phase, h_{km} denotes the channel gain between transmitter m and user k and σ^2 represents the noise power. and then use this SNR for calculating SE using Shannon's formula. So the objective function will be formula (4) where $g_{km} = |\mathbf{h}_{km}^H \mathbf{w}_{km}|^2$, $x_{km} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether UE k is served by RU m , $a_m \in \{0, 1\}$ specifies whether RU m is active, and $p_{km} \geq 0$ is the transmit power allocated from RU m to UE k .

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\{x, a, p\}} \quad & \sum_k \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\sum_m x_{km} p_{km} g_{km}}{\sigma^2} \right) \\ & - \lambda_{\text{fix}} \sum_m a_m - \sum_{k,m} p_{km} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For better clarity, we use the algorithm 1 to show the exact actions of the agent. In the first step, we define the environment variables. The system consists of 12 fixed RUs, and a predefined SNR threshold is used to determine user-centric clusters. If the SNR between a user and an RU falls below this threshold, the RU is excluded from the user's cluster. To guide the agent, invalid choices are penalized with a large

Algorithm 1: Power-SE Aware Resource Allocation with DQRL

Input: Constant Number Of RUs,
SNR threshold ($SNR_{th} = 10$ dB),
Power levels ($P_t = [0.01, 0.05, 0.1]$) W,
 $P_{newRU} = 12$ W,
Output: Optimal EE or SE RUs' selection policy.

- 1 **Environment Setup:** Initialize RUs' locations
- 2 reset Environment:
- 3 Initialize UEs with random locations
- 4 $H \leftarrow$ Channel gain matrices
- 5 Zero-Forcing precoding using (H)
- 6 **SNR** using (2)
- 7 **SE** using (3)
- 8 **Execution:** for each UE do
 - 9 **Input:** Action $= (RU_i, P_t)$
 - 10 **if** SNR(P_t, UE_j, RU_i) $< SNR_{th}$ **then**
 - 11 $reward \leftarrow -50$; // heavy Penalty for choosing low SNR threshold or invalid choice
 - 12 **else**
 - 13 $P_{cost} \leftarrow P_t + \mathbb{I}_{fixed} \times P_{newRU}$
 - 14 $r \leftarrow -[\alpha \cdot P_{cost} + (1 - \alpha)(Max_{SE} - SE_{achieved})]$; // Reward encourages power efficiency or spectral efficiency
 - 15 **end**
 - 16 Update system state
 - 17 **if** episode complete **then**
 - 18 Return (next state, reward, done, info)
 - 19 **end**
- 20 **DQRL Training:** Input layer size: ($All\ UEs \times All\ RUs \times All\ power\ levels$)
- 21 Hidden layers: Linear + ReLU activation
- 22 Output layer: Linear(action space size)
- 23 **for** each episode **do**
 - 24 $state \leftarrow$ reset Environment function
 - 25 **while** not done **do**
 - 26 **if** random $< Epsilon(\epsilon)$ **then**
 - 27 $action \leftarrow$ random action
 - 28 **else**
 - 29 $action \leftarrow \max(Policy\ network(state))$
 - 30 **end**
 - 31 Convert flat action to (RU, power) indices
 - 32 ($next\ state, reward, done, info$) \leftarrow setup Environment(action)
 - 33 Store transition in Replay buffer
 - 34 **if** buffer size \geq batch size **then**
 - 35 Sample random batch from buffer
 - 36 Calculate Q-values: $Q \leftarrow Policy\ network(states)$
 - 37 **for** each transition in batch **do**
 - 38 **if** not terminal **then**
 - 39 $target \leftarrow reward + \gamma \times \max(Target\ network(next\ state))$
 - 40 **else**
 - 41 $target \leftarrow reward$
 - 42 **end**
 - 43 **end**
 - 44 Update Policy network to minimize MSE(Q, targets)
 - 45 **end**
 - 46 **if** episode mod $N == 0$ **then**
 - 47 Update Target network \leftarrow Policy network
 - 48 **end**
 - 49 Decay $\epsilon \leftarrow \max(\epsilon_{min}, \epsilon \times \epsilon_{decay})$
 - 50 **end**
 - 51 **end**

negative reward, encouraging valid associations. At the beginning of each episode, the environment is reset: a new set of randomly positioned users is generated, the channel gain matrix

is computed, ZF precoding is applied, and the corresponding SNR and SE matrices are built. During the execution phase, the agent selects an action consisting of a specific RU and a power level based on an epsilon-greedy policy. The reward is then calculated and the agent receives a large negative reward (penalty) for invalid choice. Otherwise, the reward is calculated as a weighted trade-off between EE and SE. P_{cost} is computed as the sum of transmission power and the RU activation energy that only applied if the RU is used for the first time, determined by a binary variable $\mathbb{I}_{\text{fixed}}$ also $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the EE–SE trade-off, and SE_{max} represents the maximum achievable SE per user. When $\alpha = 1$, the policy prioritizes energy efficiency, when $\alpha = 0$, it prioritizes spectral efficiency. This optimization problem formulation ensures that the agent minimizes power consumption while maintaining acceptable SE. The negative reward arises from the combination of transmission power cost and the gap between the achieved SE and its maximum value design encourages the agent to minimize power consumption while maximizing SE, thereby driving it to effectively solve the joint optimization problem. The agent’s neural network model is a fully connected Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) with two hidden layers of 128 neurons each, used the SNR and SE matrices (one per power level) as input (system state) and outputs an action: the selected RU and power level. This process is repeated for all users within an episode, and the total reward is recorded as the final reward. Within each episode, the agent performs Q-value updates, selects actions using an epsilon-greedy policy, applies experience replay with mini-batches, and periodically updates the target network. The training progress is monitored by evaluating the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between predicted and target Q-values, ensuring stable learning and convergence to the desired policy.

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we present the simulation details, methodology, and results, highlighting the achieved improvements over different baseline. Table I outlines the parameters and hyperparameters used in the simulation setup.

TABLE I: Variable use in simulation

Simulation Parameters	
Parameter	Value
Transmit powers P_m	[10, 50, 100] mW
Noise variance σ^2	-146.424dBm
Boltzmann constant K_B	1.380649×10^{-23} J/K
Temperature in Kelvin	290 K
Path Loss Exponent	3.6
Batch size	64
Epsilon decrement	0.99
Epsilon minimum	0.001

As described in Section II, we employ an agent that operates within a dynamic environment. Consequently, in each episode, a varying number of UEs enter the network, which comprises 12 RUs. Each traffic flow remains in the network for a duration equal to one time interval, the length of which is determined by equation (1). After this interval, the traffic exits the network and is replaced by a new flow. While additional DRL baselines

Fig. 2: Valid action rate over training episodes. The figure shows the percentage of valid RU selections.

Fig. 3: Episodes total reward during training. Initially, the agent receives highly negative rewards due to invalid RU selections. As training progresses, the agent learns to avoid these actions, leading to a rapid increase and stabilization in the total reward.

(e.g., actor–critic or multi agent methods) are relevant, a fair comparison would require extensive hyperparameter tuning and matched training budgets across algorithms. In this work, we intentionally focus on a single-agent DQN to keep the controller lightweight and reduce training overhead in our setting, while explicitly capturing the EE–SE trade-off through the reward design. To ensure effective agent learning, we perform simulations over 40,000 episodes. It is also possible to enhance learning precision by adding a predefined number of steps to each episode [14].

Fig. 2 presents the percentage of valid actions taken by the agent over the course of training. A valid action refers to selecting a RU with an SNR above the defined threshold, meaning the RU is within the acceptable range to serve a user. Thanks to penalty mechanism, the agent rapidly learns to avoid selecting RUs with SNRs below the threshold or out of UE’s cluster. As shown in the figure 2, the valid action rate increases sharply during the early episodes and eventually stabilizes close to 98% to 100%. To enhance visual clarity and avoid clutter, we downsampled the original 40,000 episodes and highlighted only 200 evenly spaced data points.

Fig. 4: Total power consumption across training episodes considering $\alpha = 1$.

Fig. 5: Total SE Improvement across training episodes considering $\alpha = 0$.

As described earlier, we define a reward function with negative values to penalize undesired agent behaviors. Fig. 3 shows the evolution of the agent’s total reward over all training episodes. In the initial episodes, due to the agent’s exploratory behavior and frequent selection of invalid RUs (those with SNR below the threshold out of cluster), the total reward is highly negative. However, as training progresses and the agent begins to recognize valid actions, the frequency of invalid choices decreases. This leads to a rapid improvement in the reward, which stabilizes as the agent learns an effective policy.

After this agent gradually reducing total power consumption or increasing SE depending on the value of the trade-off coefficient α . As shown in Fig. 4, total power consumption decreases steadily during training, albeit at a slower rate compared to SE and validation metrics. This behavior occurs because power minimization contributes less strongly to the reward compared to SE optimization or heavy penalty. Fig. 4 considers the case $\alpha = 1$, which represents the opposite condition to Fig. 5 with $\alpha = 0$. In this case, because the reward is more strongly dominated by SE, improvements in spectral efficiency occur faster than reductions in power consumption. In both scenarios, the agent eventually converges to a policy:

deactivating unnecessary RUs [15] when power minimization is prioritized, selecting RUs with higher effective channel gains [4] when SE is the primary objective, or adopting a balanced strategy when α is adjusted to reflect a trade-off between the two.

Finally, we evaluate the proposed method against three baseline strategies and consider both the cumulative power consumption (in watts) and the cumulative spectral efficiency computed equation (3). The baselines are as follows. Max SE (maximum SNR) policy: Each UE is associated with the RU that provides the highest channel gain, irrespective of power consumption. This approach maximizes spectral efficiency and reliability, making it suitable for heavily loaded networks where blocking probability must remain low. Min Power Greedy policy: For each UE, the algorithm identifies all RUs with SNR above the threshold and selects the one requiring the minimum transmission power and the minimum number of active RUs. Although this approach significantly lowers energy consumption, it may choose suboptimal links in high load conditions, which increases the blocking probability and reduces overall SE. Random policy: RUs are selected randomly without considering SNR or power, leading to the poorest performance. This method exhibits high blocking probability, which increases sharply as the number of UEs grows.

As illustrated in Fig. 6, our agent adapts its behavior according to the coefficient α , operating between these baseline strategies. When $\alpha = 0.8$, the agent prioritizes energy efficiency and behaves similarly to the Min Power Greedy method, albeit with reduced SE. In contrast, when $\alpha = 0.2$, the agent emphasizes SE, yielding substantial throughput improvements at the cost of higher power consumption relative to its benchmark.

We evaluated the agent under scenarios with 12, 14, and 16 users. Owing to training across diverse conditions, the achieved reliability consistently exceeded 98%. Blocking events occurred only when no valid RU options were available (i.e., when all candidates were below the SNR threshold). This is particularly noticeable for our agent, which applies a stricter threshold to ensure more reliable associations compared to the baselines.

Overall, the results confirm that the proposed method effectively adapts to varying traffic loads and SNR constraints. By adjusting α , the agent can dynamically balance the trade off between EE and SE while maintaining high reliability.

IV. CONCLUSION

In Conclusion with the advancement of new architectures such as CF mMIMO and the transition toward next-generation wireless communications, intelligent and efficient solutions are essential to meet future demands. Traditional approaches like maximum channel gain or uniform resource allocation, while effective in the past, may no longer be sufficient for modern requirements. In this research, we propose a dynamic agent trained to make adaptive decisions based on learned policies and network conditions. This ensures adaptability to evolving requirements while maintaining high transmission quality and reliability.

Fig. 6: Comparison of the proposed DQRL agent with baseline methods under different traffic loads (12, 14, and 16 users) and reward settings. The top row (a–c) shows results for $\alpha = 0.8$, where energy efficiency is prioritized, while the bottom row (d–f) corresponds to $\alpha = 0.2$, emphasizing spectral efficiency. Metrics include (a,d) total power consumption, (b,e) spectral efficiency, and (c,f) reliability. The results demonstrate the agent’s ability to adapt its behavior according to α , effectively balancing the trade-off between energy and spectral efficiency while maintaining high reliability.

For future work, extending this framework to a multi-agent system could enable more advanced functionalities such as traffic slicing, intelligent admission control, and adaptive tuning of the α coefficient based on predicted network load to enhancing efficiency and scalability also the power model could be extended to include more detailed factors, such as load-dependent power scaling and other parameters.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the European Union under the EMPOWER-6G project (Grant agreement ID: 101120332), 6G-BRICKS project (Grant agreement ID: 101096954) and by the SUNRISE-6G project (Grant agreement ID:101139257).

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Ghafouri, J. S. Vardakas, K. Ramantas, and C. Verikoukis, “A multi-level deep rl-based network slicing and resource management for o-ran-based 6g cell-free networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 73, no. 11, pp. 17472–17484, 2024.
- [2] S. Elhoushy, M. Ibrahim, and W. Hamouda, “Cell-free massive mimo: A survey,” *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 492–523, 2021.
- [3] F. S. Vajd, M. Hadi, C. Bhar, M. R. Pakravan, and E. Agrell, “Dynamic joint functional split and resource allocation optimization in elastic optical fronthaul,” *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 4505–4515, 2022.
- [4] N. Ghafouri, J. S. Vardakas, K. Ramantas, and C. Verikoukis, “Rl-based high-level radio unit clustering and distributed unit assignment in user-centric cell-free mmimo for oran-based 6g,” in *Proc. IEEE ICC 2024*.
- [5] H. T. Dao and S. Kim, “Effective channel gain-based access point selection in cell-free massive mimo systems,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 108 127–108 132, 2020.
- [6] Ö. T. Demir, M. Masoudi, E. Björnson, and C. Cavdar, “Cell-free massive mimo in o-ran: Energy-aware joint orchestration of cloud, fronthaul, and radio resources,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 356–372, 2024.
- [7] N. Ghiasi, S. Mashhadi, S. Farahmand, S. M. Razavizadeh, and I. Lee, “Energy efficient ap selection for cell-free massive mimo systems: Deep reinforcement learning approach,” *IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 29–41, 2022.
- [8] E. Björnson, J. Hoydis, L. Sanguinetti *et al.*, “Massive mimo networks: Spectral, energy, and hardware efficiency,” *Foundations and Trends® in Signal Processing*, vol. 11, no. 3–4, pp. 154–655, 2017.
- [9] S.-N. Jin, D.-W. Yue, and H. H. Nguyen, “Spectral and energy efficiency in cell-free massive mimo systems over correlated rician fading,” *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 2822–2833, 2020.
- [10] Y. Jin, J. Zhang, S. Jin, and B. Ai, “Channel estimation for cell-free mmwave massive mimo through deep learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 10 325–10 329, 2019.
- [11] C. Desset, B. Debaillie, V. Giannini, A. Fehske, G. Auer, H. Holtkamp, W. Wajda, D. Sabella, F. Richter, M. J. Gonzalez *et al.*, “Flexible power modeling of lte base stations,” in *Proc IEEE WCNC 2012*.
- [12] M. Eskandarinia, F. Arpanaei, H. Beyranvand, H. Rabbani, Ó. G. de Dios, J. P. Fernández-Palacios, D. Larrabeiti, and J. A. Hernández, “Maximizing cost and energy savings in multi-band eons through qot-driven service deployment,” in *Proc. IEEE MeditCom 2024*.
- [13] S. Mhatre, F. Adelantado, K. Ramantas, and C. Verikoukis, “Intelligent qos-aware slice resource allocation with user association parameterization for beyond 5g o-ran-based architecture using drl,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2024.
- [14] H. Park and Y. Lim, “Deep reinforcement learning based resource allocation with radio remote head grouping and vehicle clustering in 5g vehicular networks,” *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 23, 2021.
- [15] M. Rafid, H. Ghafoor, and I. Koo, “An svm-based optimal-controller selection and path selection protocol for heterogeneous communications in sdvns,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 3828–3842, 2023.